

**THE EFFICACY OF THE SIDDHA FORMULATION *VENPOOSANI LEGIYAM* FOR
PELVIC INFLAMMATORY DISEASES – THE REVIEW**

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ABSTRACT

Background: The fundamental principle of the siddha system of medicine is strongly about the *pancha bootha theory* and *mukkutram*. The poly herbal siddha formulation *venpoosani legiyam* is the coolant drug (*thatpam*) that balance the incontinence of the heat (*pitham*). The pelvic inflammatory disease is a sexually transmitted disease caused by the bacteria chlamydia, gonorrhoea and also caused by the bacteria *e-coli*, *streptococcus* affects the uterus, fallopian tube, and ovaries. This is disease is caused by the dominance of *pitham*. **Methodology:** The sources are collected from siddha literature and various data bases. **RESULT:** The *venpoosani legiyam* can cure the pelvic inflammatory disease, by its pharmacological properties that exhibit Anti-inflammatory, Anti-bacterial, Anti-viral, Anti- microbial, Antioxidant, Anti-depressive, Analgesic, Anti-diarrheal, Anti-diabetic, Styptic, Anti-emetic, Cardiovascular protective activities. **Conclusion:** The pelvic inflammatory disease caused by the dominance of the *pitham*. So the poly herbal siddha formulation *venpoosani legiyam* can balance the incontinence of the *pitham* (*thee bootham*). This review will help to make the further studies of *venpoosani legiyam* against pelvic inflammatory disease.

KEYWORDS: Pelvic inflammatory disease, *Venpoosani legiyam*, *Pitham*, *Thatpam*.

INTRODUCTION

The fundamental principle of siddha system of medicine is strongly about the *pancha bootha theory* and *mukkutram*. The *venpoosani legiyam* is a poly herbal siddha formulation.^[1] In siddha literature, this formulation can cure the leukorrhoea and the venereal diseases (*vellainoi* and *piramiyam*) with the dosage of 5g (*punnai kai* (fruit *Calophyllum inophyllum*) size) for 45 days. The pelvic inflammatory disease is a sexually transmitted disease caused by the bacteria chlamydia, gonorrhoea and also caused by the bacteria *e-coli*, *streptococcus* affects the uterus, fallopian tube, and ovaries. In the siddha system of medicine, the *Pelvic inflammatory* disease related to the dominance of the *Pitham*. The poly herbal drug *venpoosani legiyam* can balance the incontinence of the *Pitham*.

METHODOLOGY

INGREDIENTS OF THE DRUG *VENPOOSANI LEGIYAM*

Benincasa hispida (*venpoosani*), *Pandanus odoratissimum* (*thazhai*), *Cocos nucifera* (*thennam poo*), *Citrus aurantifolia* (*ezhumitchai*), *Bos indicus* (*pasum paal*), *Saccharum officinarum* (*sarkarai*), *Cuminum cyminum* (*seeragam*), *Coriandrum sativum* (*kothumalli*),

Saussurea lappa (*kostam*), *Elettaria cardamomum* (*ela arisi*), *Myristica fragrans* (*jathikai*), *Myristica fragrans* (*sathipaththiri*), *Piper nigrum* (*milagu*), *Quercus infectoria* (*masikkai*), *Glycyrrhiza glabra* (*athimadhuram*), *Taxus baccata* (*thalisapaththiri*).^[2]

PHARMACOLOGY

***Benincasa hispida* (*Venpoosani*):** The *venpoosani juice* has several phytochemicals that are carbohydrate, glycosides, saponin, phytosterols, phenols, flavonoids, proteins, amino acids and diterpenoids has been reported. This plant exhibit pharmacological properties are antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, hepatoprotective, analgesic, acaricidal activities.^[3]

***Pandanus odoratissimum* (*Thazhai*):** The *thazhai vizhuthu* extract has phytochemicals are essential oils, flavanoids, terpenoids, saponins, phytosterols, carotenoids has been reported. This extract can exhibit pharmacological properties are anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-diarrheal, anti-pyretic, anti-tissues activities.^[4]

***Cocos nucifera* (*Thennam poo*):** The extract of *thennam poo* has phytochemicals are Flavonoids, Tannis,

alkaloids, carbohydrates, glycosides, saponins, sterols has been reported. This can exhibit properties are Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, analgesic, astringent, cardiovascular protection, styptic activities.^[5]

Citrus aurantifolia (ezhumitchai): The *pazha charru* has several phytochemicals that are citric acid, limonene, essential oils, vitamin C, and other poly phenols has been reported. This can exhibit certain properties are antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anti-bacterial, anti-diabetes, Anti tissues activities.^[6]

Bos indicus (Pasum paal): The *cow milk* has phytochemicals that are lactic acid, lactoferrin, isoflavones, omega 3 fatty acids, has been reported. This exhibit properties are Antioxidant, Anti-hyperglycemia, Anti-hypolipidemic, activities and it enhance the uterus health and immune function.^[7]

Saccharum officinarum (sarkaarai): The *saccharum officinarum* has phytochemicals are flavanoids, saccharine, Phenolic acid, has been reported. This exhibit some properties are antioxidant, wound healing activities.^[8]

Cuminum cyminum (Seeragam): The *cumin (seeragam)* has phytochemicals are flavanoids, essential oils, alkaloids, saponins, Tannis has been reported. This exhibit properties are Antioxidant, Anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetes, anti-diarrhea, anti-osteoporotic activities and it aids Digestion.^[9]

Coriandrum sativum (Kothumalli): The *coriander* has phytochemicals that are essential oils, fatty acids, Phenolic acid, sterols, flavanoids has been reported. This exhibit some properties are antioxidant, anti-microbial, anti-diabetes, neuroprotective and cardiovascular tonic activities and it aids Digestion.^[10]

Saussurea lappa (Kostam): *Kostam* has several phytochemicals are sesquiterpene, lactones, cortunolides, dehydrocostus lactone, and cyanospricin has been reported. This exhibit properties are Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-ulcer, anti-cancer, anti-microbial, hepato-protective activities.^[11]

Elleteria cardamomum (Ela arisi): The *cardamom* has phytochemicals are phenols, 1,8 cineole, Alpha terpineol, linalool, linalyl acetate, tannins, terpenoids, flavanoids, sterols has been reported. This exhibit properties are Antioxidant, anti-microbial, anti-inflammatory, anti-emetic, anti-ulcer, gastro protective activities.^[12]

Myristica fragrans (Jathikkai): The *nutmeg* has several phytochemicals that are Ligans, neoligans, myristicin, maceligan, phenypropanoids, eregenol, safrille, terpenoids has been reported. This exhibit some properties are antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, analgesic, diuretics, carminative, anti-cancer activities.^[13]

Myristica fragrans (Sathipaththiri): The *nutmeg mace* has phytochemicals are elemicin, Ligans, terpenoids, flavanoids, myristicin has been reported. This exhibit some properties are antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-bacterial, analgesic, anti-diarrheal, hypnotic activities.^[14]

Piper nigrum (Milagu): The *pepper* has several phytochemicals that are piperin, flavanoids, terpenoids, saponins, alkaloids, carotenoids has been reported. This exhibit properties are Antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anti-diabetes, anti-diarrheal, anti-depressants, analgesic activities.^[15]

Quercus infectoria (Maasikkai): The *mecca galls* has phytochemicals are Galic acid, ellagic acid, tannins, Phenolic acid Flavonoids has been reported. This exhibit some properties are anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-diarrheal, anti-bacterial, Anti-fungal activities.^[16]

Glycyrrhiza glabra (Athimadhuram): *Licorice* has phytochemicals that are glycyrrhizin, tannins, flavanoids, Licorice, saponins, coumarin, has been reported. This exhibit some properties are anti-inflammatory, anti-microbial, anti-viral, antidepressive, antiulcer, hepatoprotective activities.^[18]

Taxus baccata (Thalisapathiri): *English yew* has phytochemicals are plant sterols, taxol, taxotere, flavanoids, saponins has been reported. This exhibit some properties are antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, anti-cancer, anticonvulsant, analgesic, bronchodilator activities.^[17]

RESULT

The poly herbal siddha formulation *venpoosani legiyam* can cure the pelvic inflammatory disease, by its pharmacological properties anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anti-cancer, anti-microbial, antioxidant, anti-depressants, analgesic, styptic, cardiovascular protection, anti-viral, anti-emetic activities with the siddha literature said that leucorrhoea and venereal diseases [*Vellai and Piramiyam*].

Fig.1: Pharmacological properties in raw drugs of *venpoosani legiyam*.

CONCLUSION

According to the Siddha medical system, Pitham's dominance is the cause of pelvic inflammatory disease. Additionally, Pitham's incontinence can be balanced by the *Venpoosani Legiyam*. The current idea of treating pelvic inflammatory disease is predicated on the pharmacological properties of the medication, such as its analgesic, anti-inflammatory, antibacterial, and antimicrobial properties. Raw drugs of *Venpoosani legiyam*'s also possess these properties. Further research on *venpoosani legiyam*'s ability to combat pelvic inflammatory illness will be aided by this review.

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